
University St. Kliment Ohridski Bitola
Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality Ohrid

Conference Proceedings INSCOSES
XVII International Scientific Conference on Services Sector
INSCOSES, Ohrid, 26-27 September 2024

CIP - Каталогизација во публикација
Национална и универзитетска библиотека "Св. Климент Охридски",
Скопје

338.48(062)

33(062)

338.47(062)

640.4(062)

INTERNATIONAL Scientific Conference on Service sector INSCOSES (17 ;
2024 ; Ohrid)

Conference Proceedings INSCOSES ; XVII International Scientific
Conference on Service sector INSCOSES, Ohrid, 26-27 September 2024
[Електронски извор] / [organizing committee Aleksandar Trajkov ... и
др.]. - Текст во PDF формат, содржи 435 стр., илустр. - Ohrid : Faculty
of tourism and hospitality, 2025

Начин на пристапување (URL): <https://zenodo.org/communities/inscoses/>
(Слободен пристап). - Наслов преземен од екранот. - Опис на изворот на
ден 26.02.2025. - Библиографија кон трудовите

ISBN 978-608-4676-41-6

а) Туризам -- Собири б) Гастрономија -- Собири в) Економија -- Собири г)
Царина -- Собири

COBISS.MK-ID 65372677

Conference Proceedings INSCOSES
XVII International Scientific Conference on Services Sector INSCOSES, Ohrid,
26-27 September 2024
ISBN 978-608-4676-41-6

UDK 336.71:005.62(100)
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14987985

IDENTIFICATION AND MIGRATION OF THE BANKS' BUSINESS MODELS IN EUROPE

Ljube Jolevski, Ph.D.

University „American College” – Skopje
School of Business Economics and Management
ljube.jolevski@uacs.edu.mk

Snezana Dicevska, Ph.D.

University „St. Kliment Ohridski” – Bitola
Faculty for Tourism and Hospitality – Ohrid
snezana.dicevska@uklo.edu.mk

ABSTRACT

The business model is the way a bank works that is a way it generates income and grows over time. Each business model is unique, although similar characteristics of their business models can be found among banks. The determination of the bank's business model is a starting premise and a basic criterion for evaluating the bank's performance as a whole.

The aim of this paper is to identify the business models of the banks in Europe, but at the same time to determine their migration, i.e. change of the business model due to constantly changing internal factors, but also their inevitable adjustment to the change in the regulation and the external macroeconomic environment and the economy in general.

Although, some post-crisis trends in the structure of banks' business models have undoubtedly contributed to making them more reliable and stable, the results presented in this paper show that today there is no specific business model that is clearly superior compared to other models.

KEY WORDS: business models, banks, bank activities, identification, migration

INTRODUCTION

The business model of a bank is a multidimensional, complex and relatively new concept. The analysis of the business model, as well as the knowledge of the factors that influence the determination of an appropriate business model of the banks and its success, are essential for the operation of the banks. Considering the importance and role that banks have in the financial system and in the economy, their operations and achieved results are not only important for shareholders and depositors, but also for the economy of a country as a whole. Precisely because of this, this area deserves special attention.

Defining and identifying the business models of banks is not a simple task due to their comprehensiveness, constantly changing internal factors, but also their inevitable adaptation to changes in regulation and the external macroeconomic environment and the economy in general. There is no universal business model, i.e. "one model for all" banks.

Modern banks offer a wide portfolio of traditional banking services, but more recently, they are competing against the advance of an impressive wave of financial technology. Thus, the usual role of banks in the economy has evolved from the traditional approach of intermediation to an approach where banks offer a wide range of financial services, strengthened by revolutionary changes and innovations in the way of doing business, in order to adequately respond to trends, customer demands and strengthen their competitive advantages.

The paper contains three parts. In addition to the review of the literature on the identification of business models of banks, the second part presents an overview of the identified business models of European banks and the third part lists the most significant migrations of business models. Finally, summarized conclusions are given.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The interest in analyzing the business models of banks is particularly noticeable after the global economic and financial crisis of 2007/2008, in order to advance the professional analysis of the behavior of banks. Primarily, the interest is in finding appropriate tools for identifying the operations of banks and better understanding their financial performance and riskiness. The

literature focused on the study of bank business models does not have a long history. According to Goncharenko's (2020) research, in 2017 the number of scientific papers dealing with bank business models increased by 148% compared to 2012, with the largest number of researchers studying bank business models coming from America, Great Britain and India.

The following can be noted as more significant works that begin to analyze business models in individual banks, i.e. their identification and efficiency assessment: Ayadi et al (2011, 2014, 2016, 2019), Ayadi and de Groen (2014), Farne and Vouldis (2017), Margaerts and Vennet (2016), Brighi and Venturelli (2016), Bonaccorsi di Patti and Palazzo (2018), De Meo et al (2016), Roengpitya et al (2017), Halaj and Zochowski ECB Working Paper 2070 (2017), Venturelli et al (2020), EBA (2018), BIS (2017).

Osterwalder (2004) analyzes the business model of banks as synonymous with strategic management of the bank, which affects the risk taken, profitability and reliability of the banks. Casadesus-Masanell and Ricart (2010) consider that the business model is a direct result of the implementation of the bank's strategy. Ayadi et al. (2011) are pioneers in the analysis of business models. Their latest research from 2019 shows that the retail banking model managed better during the crisis period in terms of performance compared to other identified business models, which registered much riskier behavior before and during the year of financial crisis. The analysis of business models also showed that the regulatory requirements of the Basel standards are not suitable for all business banking models and make attempt to identify the behavior of each business model in the context of a crisis situation. They conclude that business models with a stronger focus on traditional banking are more firmly identified than models more dominated by capital market activities.

Erins and Erina (2013) analyze the business models used by the five largest banks operating in each separate Central and Eastern European (CEE) country over the period from 2006 to 2011. They distinguish four different types of business models: wholesale banks, investment banks, retail banks and universal banks. Based on an analysis of their data (the rate of return on assets and the rate of return on equity), the authors conclude that the majority of banks in the sample are universal banks.

Tomkus (2014) analyzes 63 European and American banks in the period from 2007 to 2012. The paper identifies three distinctive business models: a wholesale-oriented universal banking business model, a retail banking business model, and an investment banking business model. The study

provides evidence that banks change their business models as a reaction to changing macroeconomic environments, that is a phenomenon associated with significant events in the financial markets.

Roengpitya et al. (2014) identify the types of business models by implementing the clustering method of balance sheet data in 222 international banks in the period from 2005 to 2013. In the research are covered 34 countries from Europe, North America, Asia, Oceania and emerging economies. The study identifies three business models: retail-funded banks, wholesale-funded commercial banks and capital markets-oriented banks. They state that banks which deal mainly with commercial activities have lower costs and more stable profits than those that are more involved in capital market activities. Also, the authors conclude that crowd-funded banks engaged in traditional activities have gained popularity over the past few years precisely because of their consistent and stable performance.

Cernov and Urbano (2018) use balance sheet data and qualitative variables to identify business models in a more granular way. Although, this approach is closer to the regulatory way of evaluating business models, the lack of publicly disclosed qualitative data points to difficulties and subjectivity in the evaluation.

In the analysis, they include the diversity in the size of banks and ownership structures in European countries and make an attempt to identify the behavior of each business model in the context of a crisis situation. Jociene (2015) attempts to identify the business models adopted by nine subsidiaries of Scandinavian banks operating in the Baltic countries (Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania) for the period 2006 to 2014. The authors derive the main characteristics of banks: retail banks operating in one jurisdiction, dependence on decisions made by parent banks, risk aversion, stronger focus on interest income and high efficiency, stability orientation, average profitability with a negative trend for the future.

Venturelli et al. (2020) focus on identifying the business models of a sample of 45 listed European banking groups (with a total asset value of more than \$50 billion) from 14 countries over the period 2006 to 2015 based on the values of the main components of income. At the same time, this approach differs from the others because it does not use accounting data from the financial statements, but uses the market value of the variables, with the rationale that it is a forward-looking approach and with its help future performance can be better identified and risks arising from different business

models.

IDENTIFICATION OF THE BUSINESS MODELS

From the presented review of the literature, it can be concluded that the individual authors use different variables in their research for the identification of business models resulting from the availability of data, statistical analysis, expert judgment, as well as previous research. Mainly, business model categories are defined in terms of three dimensions:

- main activities: defining the type of activities with which the institution works and which are reflected mainly on the side of assets in its balance sheet;
- main sources of financing: defining the sources that the institution uses to finance its activities and are reflected mainly on the liability side of its balance sheet;
- the legal status.

According to the analysis of EBA (2019), 11 different types of business models have been identified shown in table 1. These business models can be grouped into four broadly defined business models: universal, retail-oriented, corporate-oriented and other specialized business models.

It is characteristic of universal banks that they are financed by deposits from customers, wholesale, foreign and/or domestic investors. Their main activities on the asset side are lending to the retail segment, the corporate sector, capital market activities and activities predominantly in the domestic and/or cross-border market. Retail-oriented banks are financed by deposits from the clients, and the main activities on the asset side are lending to the population and domestic companies with consumer and mortgage loans. Corporate-oriented banks collect and/or do not collect deposits from the clients and are aimed at financing domestic and international trade, leasing and factoring. Specialized business models refer to banks engaged in activities with securities, mortgage loans, Islamic banking and etc.

Table 1. Categories of business models in EU

Broad business model category	Business model	Main activities	Main funding
Universal banks	Cross-border banks	Retail, corporate and capital market activities; major cross-border operations	Deposits from clients, wholesale, foreign investors
	Local universal banks	Retail, corporate and capital market activities; operating predominantly in its domestic market	Deposits from clients, wholesale, predominantly funding from domestic investors
Retail oriented banks	Consumer credit banks	Consumer loans	Retail deposits
	Cooperative banks	Retail loans and domestic businesses	Retail deposits
	Savings banks	Retail banking	Retail deposits
	Mortgage banks	Mortgage loans to retail clients	Retail deposits
	Private banks	Wealth-management to high worth individuals	Retail deposits
Corporate oriented banks	Corporate-oriented banks (including leasing and factoring)	Financing of domestic and international trade, leasing and factoring	Both taking and not taking retail deposits
Specialized business models	Custodian institutions	Custodian services	Both taking and not taking retail deposits
	Banks not taking deposits	Mortgage loans	No specification
	Others specialized banks (Islamic banking, public development banks, cooperative banks)	Islamic finance, public development banks	No specification

Source: EBA, Identification of EU bank business models, p.17-20.

Referring to the 11 categories of business models, as described in Table 2, it is notable that 57% are classified as cooperative banks. The next largest categories by number are savings banks (14% of credit institutions) and domestic universal banks (10%).

The majority of bank assets (about 62%) are concentrated in universal banks, that is, about 23% in domestic universal banks and 39% in cross-border universal banks. In contrast, cooperative banks and savings banks, which have a large share of the banking market in terms of the number of credit institutions, constitute only 9% of total assets. Savings banks comprise about 5.3% of total assets.

Table 2. Number and total assets of banks by business model

Broad business model category	Business model	Number of credit institutions	Total assets (EUR million)	Share in EU total number of credit institutions (in %)	Share in EU total assets (in %)	Average size of credit institution (EUR billion)
Universal banks	Cross-border banks	82	13.793	1.5	39.2	168
	Local universal banks	552	7.933	10.4	22.6	14
Retail oriented banks	Consumer credit banks	87	367	1.6	1.0	4
	Cooperative banks	3.019	3.164	57	9.3	1
	Savings banks	734	1.872	13.9	5.3	2.5
	Mortgage banks	126	819	2.4	2.3	6.5
	Private banks	139	361	2.6	1.0	2.6
Corporate oriented banks	Corporate oriented banks (leasing and factoring)	143	1.653	2.7	4.7	11.6
Specialized business models	Custodian institutions	44	403	0.8	1.1	9
	Banks not taking deposits	87	1.744	1.6	5.0	20

Broad business model category	Business model	Number of credit institutions	Total assets (EUR million)	Share in EU total number of credit institutions (in %)	Share in EU total assets (in %)	Average size of credit institution (EUR billion)
	Others specialized banks (Islamic banking, public development banks)	279	2.934	5,3	8,3	10,5
Total		5.292	35.142	100	100	6.6

Source: EBA, Identification of EU bank business models, p. 22.

The distribution of the number of institutions according to business model differs from country to country (Table 3). Based on the dominant type of institutions, four main groups of countries are distinguished. In the first group of countries (consisting of Germany, Greece, Spain, Italy, Hungary, Austria, Poland, Portugal and Finland), dominate cooperative banks and savings banks, that is, more than 50% of their institutions are distributed in these two business models. The second group of countries: Estonia, Croatia, Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Romania, Slovenia and Slovakia - is dominated by universal banks (local universal banks or cross-border universal banks) which represent more than 50% of institutions in these countries. The third group of countries: Denmark and Norway, have savings banks as the majority of institutions (more than 50%). And the fourth group of countries: Belgium, Czech Republic, Ireland, France, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Sweden and conditionally Great Britain) have a greater diversity in the business models of the institutions, without the possibility of determining a specific business model as the dominant model of operation in these countries.

Table 3. Number of credit institutions according to the business model by country

Country	Number of credit institutions according to the business model (above 50%)
Germany, Greece, Spain, Italy, Hungary, Austria, Poland, Portugal, Finland	Cooperative banks and savings banks

Estonia, Croatia, Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Romania, Slovenia and Slovakia	Universal banks (Local and cross-border universal banks)
Denmark and Norway	Savings banks
Belgium, Czech Republic, Ireland, France, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Sweden	Diversification of the institutions without dominant model

Source: EBA, Identification of EU bank business models, p. 23.

The analysis of business models carried out by BIS (2017) on a sample of 178 banks from 34 jurisdictions for a period of 10 years (2005-2015) shows that there are four business models with the dominant participation of universal banks (Table 4).

Table 4. Distribution of banks' business models according to share of assets in total assets (in %)

Business model	North America	Europe	Asia and Pacific (Japan and Australia)	G-SIBs
Retail banks	11	34	11	13
Wholesale funded	0	10	29	0
Trading banks	18	12	7	14
Universal banks	71	44	53	73
Total	100	100	100	100

Source: BIS, Bank Business models: popularity and performance, p.11

A more detailed analysis of banks' business models that deserves attention is Ayadi's (2019) analysis, which covers a database consisting of 3.287 banks from 32 countries of the European Economic Area (EEA) and Switzerland. The sample covers more than 95% of banking assets in the EEA, and it includes 22.787 observations in the period from 2005 to 2016, so the period before and during the financial crisis is covered.

By applying the clustering methodology, confirmed by the use of Pseudo-F indices (Calinski and Harabasz), have been identified five types of business models, such as:

- Focused Retail Banks, which provide traditional services, such as approving loans to households financed by household deposits;

- Diversified Retail Type 1 Banks, which are characterized by a combination of granting loans to households and a moderate percentage of trading activities, financed primarily by household deposits;
- Diversified Retail Type 2 Banks grant loans to customers and households with a moderate percentage of trading activities, using mainly market sources of financing (i.e. debt obligations) in addition to deposits from individuals;
- Wholesale Banks are primarily engaged in interbank lending and borrowing;
- Investment banks are primarily engaged in trading and derivative activities, and are financed by retail deposits and market financing.

In terms of ownership structure, in the European banking sector, can be made a distinction between banks with shareholder value (SHV) and stakeholder value (STV). The main objective of SHV banks is to maximize shareholder profits, while STV banks have multiple objectives (eg maximizing the number of members of cooperative societies and similar institutions in terms of making a profit). Hence, these institutions qualify as "dual or multi bottom-line" institutions that have a combined goal: profit maximization for financial sustainability of banks and added value for their stakeholders. Table 5 provides data on the ownership structures that meet the listed five business models.

Table 5. Banks' business models according to the ownership structure, by share in total assets (in %)

	Focused Retail Banks	Diversified Retail Type 1	Diversified Retail Type 2	Wholesale Banks	Investment Banks	Total
Commercial	31.38	72.86	45.74	71.73	91.01	56.75
Nationalized	4.07	10.53	2.96	0.69	1.77	4.30
Shareholder value	35.44	83.38	48.71	72.42	92.78	61.06
Cooperative Banks	20.10	6.50	17.03	3.47	5.74	13.32
Savings Houses	36.53	9.48	28.72	1.92	1.30	21.13
Public Banks	7.92	0.64	5.55	22.20	0.19	4.49
Stakeholder Value	64.56	16.62	51.29	27.58	7.22	38.94
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Ayadi et al., (2019), p.22

Regarding the number of institutions (Table 6), wholesale and investment banks are mostly SHV banks, while retail banks are mostly STV banks, which is reflected in the largest participation of cooperative banks and savings banks.

Commercial banks are on average more active in investment activities and wholesale, and less in retail activities, while cooperative banks and savings banks are relatively more retail-oriented.

Table 6. Banks' business models according to the ownership structure, by % of institutions

	Focused Retail Banks	Diversified Retail Type 1	Diversified Retail Type 2	Wholesale Banks	Investment Banks	Total
Commercial	16.6	16.8	41.7	49.1	72.7	23.8
Nationalized	0.5	0.9	4.6	0.3	2.1	0.9
Shareholder value	17.1	17.7	46.3	49.5	74.7	24.8
Cooperative Banks	47.3	62.9	20.5	43.2	14.1	49.9
Savings Houses	31.5	18.3	21.2	4.5	10.1	22.7
Public Banks	2.9	0.9	11.9	2.4	1.0	2.6
Stakeholder Value	82.8	82.2	53.6	50.2	25.2	75.2
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100
Publicly listed	6.4	5.7	27.2	2.1	14.1	7.2

Source: Ayadi et al. (2019) p.20.

In terms of the organizational structure that reflects the internationalization strategy, investment banks are internationally the most active. According to the research, these banks on average have subsidiaries and/or branches in more than six European countries. This is significantly more than wholesale banks and retail banks, which cover one and two countries.

SHV banks are significantly more active internationally than STV banks, which remain domestically oriented. Hence, commercial and nationalized banks are active in an average of 2.3 and 4.2 countries, respectively, while other banks are active only, almost exclusively, in their home markets. This review should be considered from a dynamic point of view, that is, the business models of banks change their strategy of operation, especially in the internationalization part.

MIGRATION OF BANKS' BUSINESS MODELS

Banks are not expected to change their business models often. However, they may embark on a process of adapting their business models for the following reasons:

- to respond to market developments, to competition and the race to achieve higher profits, but also to status changes among competitors (mergers and acquisitions);
- to respond to decisions made and structural reforms undertaken by the regulator or the state;
- to adapt to technological transformations and financial innovations (eg Fintech, artificial intelligence, blockchain and digital currencies);
- to adapt to the macroeconomic cycle (for example significant changes in the real estate market);
- due to other reasons (for example, failures of large banks, political events, such as the exit of Great Britain from the European Union).

Figure 1. Migration of banks' business models in EU, Ayadi et al. (2019).

Although the number of banks with a certain business model is expected to remain relatively stable over time, transitions that occur more often in some business models and less in other models are evident. Thus, Ayadi et al. (2019) based on the analysis of data from 2005 to 2016 created a matrix for the

transition of business models for banks in Europe, based on which they showed that there are differences in the behavior of business models. Namely, the focused retail business model showed the greatest persistence, that is, 90% of the banks from this business model did not change it during the analyzed period. Other business models follow, such as diversified retail banks, wholesale and investment banks, which remained in the same model in a slightly smaller percentage (89%, 87%, 80% and 85% respectively).

Seven percent of diversified retail (type 1) banks and 3.8% of diversified retail (type 2) banks migrated to focused retail. Of wholesale banks, 6% migrated to investment banks, and 4.0% of investment banks migrated to wholesale banks.

Table 7. Migration of the business models by number of banks

Business model		Business models in 2007				
		Retail funded	Wholesale funded	Trading	Universal	Total
Business models in 2005	Retail funded	23	9	0	3	35
	Wholesale-funded	2	21	0	0	23
	Trading	0	0	9	0	9
	Universal	6	3	0	40	49
	Total	31	33	9	43	116
		Business models in 2013				
		Retail funded	Wholesale-funded	Trading	Universal	Total
Business models in 2007	Retail funded	29	2	0	3	34
	Wholesale-funded	16	20	0	3	39
	Trading	0	0	11	3	14
	Universal	15	1	2	26	44
	Total	60	23	13	35	131
		Business models in 2015				
		Retail funded	Wholesale-funded	Trading	Universal	Total
	Retail funded	68	1	0	0	69

Business models in 2013	Wholesale funded	4	19	0	1	24
	Trading	0	0	15	2	17
	Universal	0	0	0	43	43
	Total	72	20	15	46	153

Source: BIS, Bank Business models: popularity and performance, p. 16.

These migrations are also confirmed in the research of BIS (2017), according to which there is no significant migration of business models, as the number of banks with a retail business model has increased. In this case, the analysis is divided into 3 sub-periods: before the crisis (2005-2007), during the crisis and immediately after it (2007-2013) and the period 2013-2015 (Table 7).

Changes in the behavior of banks, but also changes in the regulatory framework, supplemented by changes in the macroeconomic and financial conditions of the market, have contributed to some of the previously most profitable business strategies showing a deterioration in financial performance, that is, they have become less sustainable. Accordingly, banks' efforts to increase profitability, and thus the stability of the banking sector, depend on their ability to adapt their business model to new circumstances. Although some post-crisis trends in the structure of banks' business models have undoubtedly contributed to banks becoming more reliable and stable, the research shows that there is no specific business model that is clearly superior in terms of risk profile and performance compared to other models.

CONCLUSIONS

In the conditions of a significant change in the regulatory framework and changes in the financial markets, the analysis of the banks' business models is an essential tool for a better understanding of the risks to which the banks are exposed in their operations. The traditional role of banks in the economy has evolved from a traditional intermediation approach to one where banks offer a wide range of financial services, such as brokerage operations, securities trading, custodial account operations, factoring and forfeiting enhanced by revolutionary changes and innovations in the way of doing a business.

The majority of European banks adopt a retail-oriented business model, with varying degrees of diversification. Despite the fact that there are usually migrations from one business model to another, the business models of European banks are basically stable, that is, there is a low percentage of

migration. When it comes to migrations between business models, it can be said that they are in line with the profound changes in banking. A greater migration towards a diversified retail banking model can be noted, with a simultaneous reduction of banks with wholesale business models and investment banking. The latter, on average, are more profitable, but also riskier in terms of their individual contribution to systemic risk and show less resistance to shocks. In this context, migrations to business models aimed at retail financing seem to represent a positive development in European banking, given the fact that from a systemic point of view these banks are less risky, better capitalized and have more stable financial performance. Moreover, they make a positive contribution to the real economy.

The analysis of business models can serve to determine the relative contribution of each identified business model to the systemic risk during the economic cycle, as well as to complete the financial stability framework. Adding to all this is the fact that more recently, financial technology has created further challenges and new risks in the financial sector that have yet to be researched.

REFERENCES:

- Ayadi, R. & De Groen W. (2014), *Banking business models monitor 2014 – Europe*, Centre for European Policy Studies and International Observatory on Financial Services Cooperatives.
- Ayadi, R. & Arbak, E. & Groen, W. (2011), “Business Models in European Banking: A Pre- and Post-Crisis Screening”, *SSRN Electronic Journal*.
- Ayadi, R., Cucinelli, D. De Groen, W. (2019), *Banking Business Models Monitor, Performance, Risk Response to Regulation and Resolution 2005-2017*.
- Casadesus-Masanell, R. and Ricart, J.E. (2010), From strategy to business models and onto tactics, *Long range planning*, Vol.43, p. 195-215.
- Cernov, M. & Urbano, T. (2018), Identification of EU Bank Business Models, European Banking Authority, Research Paper, No. 2.
- EBA (2019), Identification of EU bank business models.
- Erins, I. U. and Erina, J. (2013): "Bank Business Models and The Changes in CEE Countries." *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology*, Vol. 7.
- Goncharenko, T. (2020). “From Business Modelling to the Leadership and Innovation in Business: Bibliometric Analysis (Banking as a Case)”, *Business Ethics and Leadership*, Volume 4, Issue 1, ISSN -2520-6311.

-
- Jociene, A. (2015), Scandinavian bank subsidiaries in the Baltics: Have they all behaved in a similar way, *Intellectual Economics*, Vol. 9, Issue 1, p.43-54.
- Osterwalder, A. (2004), The Business Model Ontology—A Proposition in a Design Science Approach. PhD Thesis, University of Lausanne, Switzerland.
- Roengpitya, R., Tarashev, N. and Tsatsaronis, K. (2014), "Bank business models," *BIS Quarterly Review*, (December), p.55-65.
- Roengpitya, R., Tarashev, N., Tsatsaronis, K., and Villegas, A. (2017), "Bank business models: popularity and performance", *BIS Working Papers*, No 682.
- Tomkus, M. (2014), Identifying business models of banks: Analysis of Biggest Banks from Europe and United States of America, Cluster analysis of business model identifying variables, Aarhus University, Department of Economics and Business, Aarhus.